

Burnup Modeling of an Accelerator-Driven Subcritical Reactor Applicable to External Neutron Sources and High-Energy Neutron Cross Sections

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the Belgian MYRRHA accelerator-driven subcritical reactor (ADS) system, aiming to establish a full-cycle burnup simulation methodology for the MYRRHA system. The subcritical core was modeled using MCNP to simulate both the proton-induced spallation reaction and the neutron transport behavior. The SCALE/ORIGEN module was employed in combination with TENDL high-energy neutron cross-section data to develop a burnup calculation method applicable to environments with an external neutron source and covering the high-energy neutron range. In addition, the computational workflow was fully automated and implemented as a program named NAADS (NARI Automated ADS Depletion System), which performs full-cycle burnup calculations for ADS and automatically generates key parameters and figures. Simulation results show that when the MYRRHA subcritical core is loaded with 30% Pu-MOX fuel, the calculated results are highly consistent with the reference parameters provided by SCK-CEN, demonstrating the credibility of the developed model. When the core is reloaded with Pu+MA (Minor Actinide, MA) mixed fuel, the system effectively burns transuranic elements, achieving both waste volume reduction and a significant decrease in disposal time. Furthermore, scaling the thermal power of MYRRHA up to the EFIT design value of 400 MWt would enable the consumption of up to 111.33 kg of transuranic elements per year.

Keywords: Accelerator Driven System, MCNP, ORIGEN, Burnup, Transmutation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Accelerator-Driven Subcritical Reactor (ADS) system has become an important direction in international nuclear research due to its advantages in handling high-level radioactive waste and its inherent safety characteristics. This study focuses on the Belgian MYRRHA (Multi-purpose hYbrid Research Reactor for High-tech Applications) system, aiming to establish a comprehensive simulation methodology that includes burnup calculation, automated workflow development, and the integration of high-energy neutron data libraries to support accurate modeling.

Because the MCNP [1] code cannot perform burnup calculations in fixed source mode, this study adopts the ORIGEN module in the SCALE [2] code system to conduct depletion calculation suitable for environments driven by a proton accelerator with an external neutron source. In addition, the TENDL-2023 (TALYS-based Evaluated Nuclear Data Library) [3]—a high-energy neutron cross-section library jointly developed by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), and the Nuclear Research and Consultancy Group (NRG)—was incorporated into the ORIGEN. This library provides evaluated nuclear reaction data for neutrons up to 200 MeV, enhancing the accuracy and completeness of simulations involving high-energy neutrons generated by proton spallation reactions.

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2. MYRRHA Subcritical Core System and NAADS Code

2.1. Introduction to the MYRRHA Subcritical Core System

The MYRRHA subcritical core model developed in this study was designed based on the technical report provided by SCK-CEN [4]. The subcritical core consists of 56 fuel assemblies with a total thermal power of 63 MWt, driven by spallation neutrons generated from a proton beam. Each MYRRHA fuel assembly is a 65-cm-high hexagonal bundle containing 127 cylindrical MOX fuel rods, with 3.5-cm-thick reflector materials placed at both the top and bottom ends. The proton beam generated by the proton accelerator has an energy of 600 MeV and is directed onto the LBE at the center of the core.

In this study, the MYRRHA subcritical core was divided into 50 fuel nodes (5 radial groups and 10 axial layers). In the MCNP modeling of the MYRRHA system, vertically connected fuel rods were constructed using the TRCL translation technique. In this approach, different material numbers are assigned to fuel segments at various axial heights, and these numbered segments are then relocated to their designated positions using TRCL translation. This method significantly simplifies the preparation of MCNP input files. MCNP was run in fixed-source mode to simulate spallation reactions induced by the proton beam striking the LBE. The proton reaction cross-section data were taken from the TENDL-2012 library, and for proton energies exceeding the library's upper limit, MCNP's built-in physics models were employed.

For the core configuration, the fuel assemblies were radially divided into five concentric fuel zones from the inner to outer regions, and axially divided into ten segments, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. MCNP Simulation of the MYRRHA Subcritical Core System.

2.2. Introduction to TENDL and AMPX

TENDL-2023 is released in the ENDF-6 standard format and contains neutron reaction cross-section data for over 2,800 nuclides. The neutron fission reaction cross sections in TENDL are available for energies up to 200 MeV. To convert these data into the format required by ORIGEN, the AMPX-6 [5] code must be used. AMPX is a nuclear data processing code developed by the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL). It is designed to handle all nuclear data libraries used within the SCALE code system. In order to make the TENDL neutron reaction cross sections, after conversion by AMPX, compatible with ORIGEN and visualizable in the SCALE Fulcrum software, the default AMPX TEMPLATE was modified, as shown in Fig. 2. After the conversion, a 255-group neutron cross-section library has been completed, covering neutron energies up to 200 MeV. A comparison of the neutron fission cross sections for Pu-239 and Am-241 between TENDL-2023 and JEFF 3.0/A is shown in Fig. 3. The major differences are observed in high-energy reactions such as (n,n') , $(n,2n)$, $(n,3n)$, and (n,γ) ,

particularly in the neutron energy region approaching 20 MeV. Beyond 20 MeV, only the TENDL library provides cross-section data, highlighting its importance for high-energy neutron simulations.

Branching ratios for neutron capture reactions are obtained from the TENDL-2023 library, stored in ENDF-6 format (MF8, MF9, and MF10 sections). These data are processed using the AMPX POLIDENT module in combination with the LIPTON module to calculate isomer production cross sections and the corresponding isomer production yields for all relevant isotopes.

Since the maximum neutron energy covered by the TENDL library is limited to 200 MeV, approximate treatments are applied to neutrons with energies exceeding this limit. Two approaches are considered: (1) assigning neutrons with energies above 200 MeV to the 200 MeV energy group, and (2) neglecting neutrons above 200 MeV. The neutron flux above 200 MeV is found to be very low, and neutron-induced reaction cross sections exhibit a decreasing trend at energies above approximately 100 MeV. Consequently, the influence of these approximations on the final transmutation results is negligible within the scope of this study. In future work, nuclear data libraries extending to higher neutron energies will be incorporated when available.

Figure 2. Flowchart of Multi-Group Neutron Cross Section Generation Using AMPX.

Figure 3. Comparison of Neutron Reaction Cross Sections between TENDL-2023 and JEFF 3.0/A, Pu-239(Up) and Am-241 (Down).

2.3. Introduction to the NAADS Code

In this study, the MYRRHA subcritical core was divided into 50 fuel nodes (5 radial groups and 10 axial Segmentation). Burnup calculations require integration of MCNP (neutron flux/energy spectra) and ORIGEN (depletion calculation) with data feedback, resulting in a complex workflow. To address this, an automated tool named NAADS (NARI Automated ADS Depletion System) was developed using Python, aiming to standardize the workflow and improve computational efficiency.

NAADS extracts MCNP results using MCNPtools[6], executes MCNP remotely on a 170 threads workstation server, and runs ORIGEN locally on a personal computer. It automates the generation of

MCNP/ORIGEN input files, performs full-cycle burnup calculations, and produces graphical outputs. The computational workflow is illustrated in Fig. 4.

For proton-induced reactions below 200 MeV, proton reaction cross sections from the TENDL-2012 library are employed. For proton energies above 200 MeV, neutron production is calculated using the CEM03.03 physics model implemented in MCNP.

NAADS provides three options for initializing the nuclide inventory:

- `mcnp`: for fresh fuel (beginning of cycle), reading data from the MCNP .o file;
- `origen`: for irradiated fuel, reading data from the ORIGEN .f71 file;
- `manual`: allowing users to manually input atomic densities.

NAADS supports two operational modes:

- `beam`: the proton beam intensity (mA) is fixed, and the core power decreases as burnup rises;
- `power`: the total core power (MW) is fixed, and the system automatically adjusts the proton beam intensity (convergence error $< 0.1\%$), with the beam intensity increasing as burnup rises.

Figure 4. Flowchart of Burnup Calculation in the NAADS Tool.

3. Simulation Results

3.1. Burnup Calculation Results of the MYRRHA Subcritical Core

This study focuses on the MYRRHA subcritical core to analyze its power maintenance strategy, accelerator intensity adjustment requirements, and fuel burnup behavior. The fuel assemblies consist of MOX fuel provided by SCK-CEN, composed of 30% Pu and 70% U-238, as shown in Table I left column. The initial cycle physics parameters are compared with the reference data provided by SCK-CEN in Table II, showing good agreement between the calculated results and the design specifications. Although there are some differences in the average core neutron flux, this may be attributed to differences in the definition of the core region.

In current international ADS system designs, a common operational strategy is to maintain a stable core power. Within the core, as the number of fission reactions increases, the quantity of fissile nuclides gradually decreases. Therefore, to sustain the same core power, the injected proton beam intensity must be increased. The required initial accelerator design intensity is 2.1529 mA, which rises to 2.5718 mA at the end of the cycle (below the design maximum of 4 mA), as shown in the left of Fig. 5.

Simulation results indicate that the proton accelerator intensity increases gradually over time (adjusted every 10 days), while the effective neutron multiplication factor, k_{eff} , decreases by $-0.00743 \Delta k$ from the beginning to the end of the cycle. This confirms that adjusting the external neutron source intensity can effectively maintain stable operation of the ADS core, as illustrated in the right of Fig. 5.

Table I. Initial atomic ratios of nuclear fuel compositions for the two considered cases.

Atomic Ratio 30% Pu / 70% U-238 MOX fuel		Atomic Ratio 60% Pu / 40% MA fuel	
U-234	6.058E-05	Np-237	3.478E-02
U-235	1.704E-03	Pu-238	2.002E-03
U-238	2.344E-01	Pu-239	4.268E-02
Pu-238	2.275E-03	Pu-240	2.273E-02
Pu-239	5.641E-02	Pu-241	7.070E-03
Pu-240	2.666E-02	Pu-242	2.392E-03
Pu-241	5.289E-03	Am-241	6.719E-02
Pu-242	7.536E-03	Am-243	1.179E-02
Am-241	2.332E-03	Cm-243	2.096E-05
O-16	6.634E-01	Cm-244	1.349E-03
		Cm-245	3.729E-04
		Mg-24	2.128E-01
		O-16	5.948E-01

Table II. Neutronic Parameter Calculation Results Compared with SCK·CEN.

	SCK·CEN	NARI
k-eff	0.95205	0.95240
Neutron Flux in the Innermost Fuel Region (n/cm²·s)	2.39E+15	2.48E+15
Average Core Neutron Flux (n/cm²·s)	1.38E+15	1.67E+15
Number of Neutrons Produced per Proton	13.85	14.85

 Figure 5. Variation of Proton Beam Intensity and k_{eff} over Time in the MYRRHA Subcritical Core

The MCNP simulation results show that the core power distribution exhibits a reasonable spatial gradient, consistent with the design expectations. Both power and neutron flux are concentrated in the central region of the core, as illustrated in Fig. 6. The maximum power peak occurs at the center of the core, closest to the proton beam source, with a peak value of 1.63 times the average core power. The overall core power is slightly shifted toward the bottom, primarily because the proton beam is directed from top to bottom and there is no LBE target within the beam tube. This distribution is consistent with the expected neutronic behavior and design specifications of the MYRRHA subcritical core.

The neutron energy spectrum indicates that the majority of the neutron flux (approximately 95%) is contributed by fission neutrons, while a small fraction (around 5%) originates from spallation neutrons produced by the proton beam and LBE target reactions. The energy of spallation neutrons can reach up to 600 MeV, as shown in Fig. 7. It is noteworthy that regions closer to the proton beam source contain higher-energy neutrons, while areas farther from the core center exhibit lower-energy neutrons. This is primarily due to the migration of protons within the core and their deceleration caused by Coulomb interactions.

After a 90-day operational cycle, significant changes in the fuel composition were observed: 2.267 kg of Pu-239 and 3.972 kg of U-238 were consumed. The minor actinide Am-241 was reduced by approximately 20 g, while about 178 g of Am-243 was simultaneously produced, as shown in Figs. 8. These results indicate that, while the ADS system consumes existing transuranic elements, it also generates new long-lived nuclides through transmutation reactions. The amounts of consumption and production are closely related to the initial fuel composition.

Figure 6. Power Distribution in the MYRRHA Subcritical Core.

Figure 7. Neutron Energy Spectrum in the MYRRHA Subcritical Core.

Figure 8. Time-dependent Variation of Transuranic Element Inventory in the MYRRHA Subcritical Core.

3.2. Burnup Calculation Results for Pu+MA Mixed Fuel

After replacing the fuel with Pu+MA (Minor Actinide) mixed fuel, the reactor characteristics of the MYRRHA subcritical core were analyzed and compared with the previous case using 30% Pu MOX fuel. To effectively consume MA nuclides, the fuel was changed to Pu+MA mixed fuel with a higher MA fraction in the heavy metal (HM) content (Pu:MA=40:60, with the heavy metal oxide to MgO ratio of 86:14). The fuel is still a heavy metal oxide fuel. MgO is added as an inert diluent in the fuel matrix to prevent the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) from becoming too high, while the main fuel composition remains uranium and plutonium oxides. The initial atomic ratios are shown in the right column of Table I.

At the beginning of the cycle, the effective neutron multiplication factor, k_{eff} , reached 0.95746. The comparison of initial cycle k_{eff} values and other parameter with 30% Pu MOX fuel calculation results is shown in Table III.

Table III. Comparison of Calculation Results between MOX Fuel and Pu+MA Fuel.

	MOX Fuel 30% Pu +70% U-238	Pu (40%)+ MA (60%) with MgO
k-eff	0.95789	0.95746
Neutron Flux in the Innermost Fuel Region (n/cm²·s)	2.3674e+15	2.0764e+15
Average Core Neutron Flux (n/cm²·s)	1.6057e+15	1.3337e+15
Number of Neutrons Produced per Proton	14.85	14.70
Initial Proton Beam Intensity per Cycle (mA)	2.1529	2.3623
Final Proton Beam Intensity per Cycle (mA)	2.5718	2.6001
Pu Consumption per Cycle (kg)	2.267	1.887
U Consumption per Cycle (kg)	3.972	-0.018
MA (Np+Am+Cm) Consumption per Cycle (kg)	-0.450	3.958

Note: Negative values indicate a net increase rather than depletion.

Using the same operational strategy of maintaining a constant core power, the proton beam intensity at the beginning of the cycle was 2.3623 mA and increased to 2.6001 mA at the end of the cycle. The change in k_{eff} from the beginning to the end of the cycle was $-0.00434 \Delta k$, smaller than that of the 30% Pu MOX fuel case ($-0.00743 \Delta k$), indicating a smaller reactivity variation and higher core stability. The core power distribution, compared with MOX fuel, is more concentrated in the central region of the core. The initial fuel loading was approximately 685 kg of heavy metal (HM), with a relatively high fraction of MA nuclides (Np, Am, Cm). After a 90-day operational cycle, the MA nuclides were effectively consumed: about 2.012 kg of Np, 1.887 kg of Pu, and 4.250 kg of Am were depleted. However, approximately 2.304 kg of Cm was produced, as shown in Fig. 9. The production of Cm nuclides is due to the β^- decay of Cm-242 following neutron capture by a large amount of Am-241 in the fuel.

Figure 9. Nuclide Inventory Changes in Pu+MA Fuel.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study successfully established a burnup calculation methodology for the MYRRHA Accelerator-Driven Subcritical Reactor (ADS) system, addressing the limitations of conventional MCNP in performing burnup calculations under subcritical conditions. The study employed the ORIGEN module within the SCALE system and incorporated the TENDL high-energy neutron cross-section data to develop the NAADS (NARI Automated ADS Depletion System) tool, capable of handling high-energy neutron calculations.

NAADS can automatically perform full-cycle burnup calculations for ADS, making it one of the simulation tools suitable for environments with external neutron sources and a high-energy neutron spectrum. The high consistency of the calculated results with SCK-CEN reference parameters demonstrates the reliability of the established methodology.

In application assessments, replacing the subcritical core fuel with Pu+MA mixed fuel effectively consumes transuranic elements, contributing to the reduction of high-level radioactive waste. For MYRRHA (63 MWt) under a 90-day operational cycle, approximately 5.845 kg of transuranic elements can be consumed. When scaled proportionally to the thermal power of the European EFIT [7] ADS (400 MWt), it could burn about 111.33 kg of transuranic elements per year, close with EFIT's claimed 120 kg. These results highlight the nuclear transmutation benefits of ADS systems for future high-level radioactive waste management and demonstrate their significant potential to shorten disposal timelines.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Los Alamos National Laboratory, *Monte Carlo N-Particle® Transport Code System Version 6.2*. CCC-850, LANL, Feb. 2023.
- [2] W. A. Wieselquist and R. A. Lefebvre, *SCALE 6.3.1 User Manual*. ORNL/TM-SCALE-6.3.1, ORNL, Feb. 2023.
- [3] "TALYS-based evaluated nuclear data library." (2023). URL https://tendl.web.psi.ch/tendl_2023/tendl2023.html
- [4] A. Stankovskiy, *Homogenized neutronic model of MYRRHA 1.6 sub-critical and critical cores*. SCK-CEN/25111463, 2017. (Intellectual property data under the MOU between NARI and SCK-CEN)
- [5] D. Wiarda, M. E. Dunn, N. M. Greene, M. L. Williams, C. Celik, and L. M. Petrie, *AMPX-6: A Modular Code System for Processing ENDF/B*. ORNL/TM-2016/43, ORNL, Apr. 2016.
- [6] C. J. (C. J.) Solomon, C. Bates, and J. Kulesza, *The MCNPTools Package: Installation and Use*. LANL, XCP-3, Mar. 30, 2017.
- [7] C. Artioli, X. Chen, F. Gabrielli, G. Glinatsis, P. Liu, W. Maschek, C. Petrovich, A. Rineiski, M. Sarotto, and M. Schikorr. "Minor actinide transmutation in ADS: the EFIT core design." In *International Conference on the Physics of Reactors*, Interlaken, Switzerland (2008).